

The Impact Of Language On Society

Afraa Ahmed Abdelkareem Ahmed

Article Info

Article History

Received:
December 28, 2024

Accepted:
March 30, 2025

Keywords :

Language, Tarazan,
American Literature,
Philosophically,
Religiously, Educationally

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15109237

Abstract

The Shortage of any discipline came from gaining or not the titles the nouns as it is said in language actually it is named.

The most or the less to recognize people traditions, customs and habits in their language. Any group of people or it is said a community. The establishment of careers through the world is through experience in language and how to treat people. When it is considered to be a fraction of situations among the capacity of deeds then a shed is thrown to language and its users and usage. The consistency of struggling through life with one language is pointed to be strange recently. For certain degradations is summing the eclipses of walking slowly through time confliction is to control the pass way of someone life and this impossible.

Introduction

Through the generations many stories of persons who live or start their life's without knowing a language. It will be a story itself to tell. The story of TARAZAN of the APES by Edgar Rice Burroughs. Then a film produced by Walt Disney Feature Animation and released by Walt Disney Pictures based on the European and American literature. Also Hai Bin Yagzan at Arabic literature, who wrote it Ibn Tufail the Islamic Arabic Philosopher. Ibn Tufail wrote about a child who has been lost in a Jungle so the child grew up with animals. Then the aim from the story from Ibn Tufail was philosophically, religiously, educationally and ethically based to prove the existence of a creator for the world. The story of Robinson Crusoe he started his life in a jungle with animals not with humans. He didn't contact any human for twentyfive years till he gets a bit old.

The idea is How to start a life in a jungle among animals and continue to live (critical question mark). The Human being can bare to some extent this in the writer's opinion but through life patience and very long consistent baring life difficulties so he is frozen because to stop doing it what is the benefit.

Then if here it started to become aware of the philosophy behind the story is to make a stress on stories of life itself and how a person can persist or hang on the stability of ongoing life. If the person die or continue to live, so what is the print he/she put through his /her life to the other generations this the thing. The story continues to react on the opinion of the writer of life itself. How life to be continued without sharing people special ideas. So the normal life is to live among society and have a role in it and share different things with people cooperation and this is life.

The writer thinks this the philosophy behind it.

The importance of language in our life is like to say what is the importance to live itself , exchanging anything with people around you. Perhaps the participants in one conversation will be offering a task of following data and information through experiences.

It's clear here the importance of language in Hai Bin Yagzan's life also TARAZAN's life. A sextent to the shortage of time of the story itself. This can be depended on several opinions to criticize it favorably or unfavorably. The circumstances of any language in the life of a person depend on his or her strict character and the point of degradation and plotting the strength of watching the improvement of personality speech. The holding of certain responsibilities over shoulders make the task of learning a bit difficult although the task itself is a learning thing in all life or in a certain points in life.

The fiction can be a message to true life but still it will be hence and then a story or a novel.

In taking the task of English as a globalization language or domineering language it depend on the proof and judge of a lot of people's life.

The crucial material to some extent expand the facility of a language or decrease it as for the struggling of a language as a subject or a course.

When being invested in language learning and the importance of knowing other languages, it is a full bright idea to communicate

all around the world. The speech of someone make a person mechanically concentrate or not, this according to the words themselves. The power to attract people to listen to you on a linkage of time and through amount of strong vocabulary according to the issue.

Here to find certain vocabulary or what is called jargon to speak in education is different to speak politics, law, medical, normal chat between people and so on different purposes in life.

The thing is vitality of languages in human being life is through wide exchange of issues.

The blending facility in Human life is to extract the medieval collapse on human facilities and needs as user of discoveries through the generations and his inventions. Then distribution and improvement through all life. The skip of certain use of language is provincial and hinting to decades of usage.

The listening to a language like an art the one can recognize what he or she meant from the tone of the voice from the tackling of the face muscles.

The case here to speak of experience in life in various languages how people talk. How do they feel how do they express on their faces.

The concordance of ability to speak a language with a lot of people different circumstances and situations. Here a bit shadow on the scholars and their theories on learning a language.

The behaviorists theory he was Pavlov a Russian scientists with Skinner an American Scholar. They make experiments on dogs. The thing is that they spoke of verbal communication in five steps they are imitation, practice, reinforcement, habit formation and generation.

Then the Innatists or what is called the mentalist theory. This is the famous scholar Scholar Noam Chomsky. He said that any person is ready to speak a language and a device (apparatus) in his brain that enable him to learn a language. That is called by him (LAD) or language acquisition device. Later on it was named universal grammar or what is abbreviated (UG). The importance of this they spoke of the critical period of age of any person. According to the writer from three years old till eleven years old. This is the period the person acquire a language.

Then the third scholar Krashen who spoke of five hypothesis. The first hypothesis is important, because he spoke about the difference between acquiring and learning. There is a depth in acquiring a language it is from a person's childhood. Frequently far a bit for learning it is from different institutes mainly schools.

The crucial thing is that people from old generations spoke languages and learn languages. The point is to try to put theories on how people learn. And other theories on how to teach languages like Grammar Translation Method. So Scholars through the nineteenth century try to stablish theories, hypothesis, opinions and ideas on how to teach and how to learn a foreign language. This is the thing through wide spread defendant of knowledge. The distribution of certain active work on scientific researches all over the world.

When the writer speak of cruciality, importance and vitality of language learning is the whole world need users to use languages

References

1. [robinsoncrusoe book - Search](#)
2. [Robinson Crusoe | Summary, Author, Characters, & Facts | Britannica](#)
3. [robinsoncrusoe free online book - Search](#)
4. [robinsoncrusoe originally published - Search Videos](#)
5. https://www.bing.com/search?pglt=299&q=%D8%AD%D9%8A%D9%8A+%D8%A8%D9%86+%D9%8A%D9%82%D8%B8%D8%A7%D9%86&cvid=872c01c3a2df487e9e34f64f9e2e88b4&gs_lcrp=EgRlZGdlKgYIABBFgDkyBggAEEUYOdIBCTM4MDk3ajBqMagCALACAA&FORM=ANSPA1&PC=LCTS
6. https://www.bing.com/search?pglt=299&q=Tarazan&cvid=9d37e77229d8410a890b2d34a1dadcbc&gs_lcrp=EgRlZGdlKgYIABBFgDkyBggAEEUYOTIGCAEQABhAMgYIAhAAGEAyBggDEC4YQDIGCAQLlhAMgYIBRAAGEAyBggGEC4YQDIGCAcQLlhAMgYICBAAGEDSAQg4NjA3ajBqMagCALACAA&FORM=ANSPA1&PC=LCTS

Author Information

Dr. Afraa Ahmed Abdelkareem Ahmed, PhD

Kingdom Of Saudi Arabia

Jazan University

University College of Farasan Island

English Department, Advisory Member
